

Can we replace education with e-learning?

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OVERVIEW

With the evolution of globalization and the worldwide expansion of technological attributes, it could be stated that e-learning has become a vital component for the success of the education sector, corporate matters and many other related fields and industries. E-learning is considered to be a mode of a learning system where the teaching is based with the use of varying electronic sources (Amarneh, Alshurideh, Al Kurdi, & Obeidat, 2021)[1]. This mitigates the requirement of the physical presence of students in an academic setting, where individuals can receive their education through an online presence. With the emergence of the unexpected pandemic of Covid-19, it could be seen that people had to face with various hardships to physically interact with each other, and the use of online platforms namely Microsoft teams and Zoom started to be used at a high degree for the need of continuation of providing an education for students. Thus, it had been observed that such online platforms and tools have supported immensely for a proper continuation of education for students around the world. Within this study, the discussion with regard to how Covid has drove the current world to utilize e-learning platforms within the education sector will be discussed, with the possibility to replace education with e-learning.

DISCUSSION : ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES

E-learning or electronic learning can be beneficial to achieve many criteria if used in a righteous way. With the emergence of e-learning, it has enabled students to learn at their own paces with independent learning at one's own will. With the rapid increment of Covid-19 pandemic,

it is challenging to hold physical classes due to the unexpected spread of the pandemic, where the probability for a fast spread of diseases is likely to occur if physical classes are taken place. Thus, e-learning enables to deliver course studies from anywhere regardless of time constrains in an effective and efficient mode (Arkorful, 2014)[2]. However, there are some limitations of virtual classrooms for students who prefer physically attending lectures over virtual studying. Even though virtual learning is favorable for students with visual, auditory, and learning styles relating to reading and writing, students with kinesthetic learning might face challenges since they tend to learn through physical activities and actually engaging with their peer groups to capture educational criteria on their minds. Kinesthetic learning style is where the tactile learning style of the individual is by participating in actual physical tasks and activities, rather than looking or listening for the lecturers' explanations. Such group activities which require an involvement of a physical connection between parties is not to be seen in the online platform. Even though some activities take place in the online classrooms for a certain extent, not all the students are willing to participate when it comes to conducting such events virtually. Therefore, an effective outcome is not achieved in most scenarios. Thus, this creates a hardship for certain students, mainly for individuals with kinesthetic learning style. Moreover, students may not be willingly participating for sessions when virtual classes take place for a long period of time, and on certain cases where the camera of the student is turned off, they might be engaging in other tasks rather than actually listening and writing down effective notes (Doulík, Skoda, & Šimonová, 2017)[3].

Unlike in a physical classroom, e-learning also enables students to easily revisit previous course studies due to the availability of a wide range of recordings of study materials that are accessible for students, which highlights the flexibility for them to learn at their own pace, by repeating and listening to the same recordings during the circumstances where they face a doubting section. Moreover, if a student come across a problematic area, they can always consult their lecturers or peer groups through various methods. These methods include via phone call conversations, virtual group discussions, private chats from teams, zoom, WhatsApp, and many other online platforms and social media networks (Arkorful, 2014)[2]. On the other hand, the learning pace of students differ from individual to individual. Thus, when virtual classrooms have a higher number of students, it may be hard for the lecturers to attend to the needs of each and every student and understand the pace of all students one by one, where the individual attention for all the students will not be provided. This can cause hardships for students with relatively a slow learning pace, causing them to fall behind. Therefore, this can be an unavoidable factor when it comes to virtual classrooms over physical classes, with the lack of individual attention for all the students. In addition, e-learning requires more time management skills and motivation to complete tasks on your own. Thus, self-dependency is higher when it comes to online learning when compared to physically attending and visiting classes. Students who lack time management skills can struggle with on time completion of tasks and has a tendency to give up on studies midway. This can also cause a negative environment for the overall education sector as well (Kumar, Saxena, & Baber, 2020)[5]. In addition, the lack of social interactions with the continuous following of online learning can cause a hindrance for the inability for students to interact well in a social setting, and increase the mental stress of students, where it is also not healthy for people to stare at a screen whole day, rather than actually speaking with peers and interacting with their lecturers. Also, when students meet new lecturers, it would be challenging to build a fast connection with the superiors in an online platform when compared with actually meeting the lecturers and

connecting. Thus, it would create hardships for lecturers as well to understand the students crowd and their different potentials of learning capabilities.

Another remarkable positive attribute of e-learning is the low and reduced costs for both the student and lecturer. If it were a physical classroom, the student will have to have a separate timeline to get ready and actually go for the classroom, while the lecturer will also have to do the same. The university is also benefited with the reduced cost of accommodation, electricity, physical coursework materials and many more. Since the course materials and assignment briefs are provided online through scan copies, this also helps to reduce wastage of unnecessary printing of paper.

Costs relating to both time and money is not undertaken to actually join for a virtual setting, where the learner can access to the classroom with a single press of a button and the ease for the lecturer to conduct the session from anywhere. This further depicts the conservation of valuable resources such as time and money for individuals in an effective manner, if used in the righteous ways (Karim Abed, 2019)[4]. But there are limitations with e-learning when it comes to issues with having a stable and a fast accessibility for an internet connection and unexpected power cuts. Also, for students living in rural areas, a proper flow of internet connectivity will not be provided and in certain cases, they will not be having proper technological tools like phones and laptops let alone an internet connection to join for an online classroom. This can demotivate students at times to do their studies in an effective manner. Moreover, when working from home, if the individual lacks proper time management skills, it can deviate the work life balance of students, where the student will lack the ability to manage their studies and household work whilst at home.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be seen that e-learning has played a vital role in uplifting the standard of education in the midst of the ongoing pandemic that is currently revolving around the world. This may be useful for continuous learning for

students, but a total replacement of e-learning from a physical education would not be beneficial in my opinion as per the above discussion points, where the tendency for certain students to fall behind will incur apart from the hardships that may be caused for the individuals living in certain villages with limited technological tools and improper practices of balance between studies and household tasks. Thus, it would be practical if a hybrid situation is imposed, with the combination of both virtual and physical classrooms. Universities can limit the number of students attending for a certain session and impose other safety standards and health regulations to avoid the spread of Covid within classrooms. Such health measures include maintenance of proper distance in between students and desks, engaging students to continuously use sanitizers and to wash their hands at all times needed, and more importantly to ensure that students with any sort of sicknesses would not be attending the University premises. Moreover, Universities can also hold one on one meetings between students and lecturers or tutors, where students who requires and wish to participate on such physical sessions can schedule a meeting with their lecturers in a situation where they want to discuss certain areas of doubts and in need of clarification. Such varying methods will support universities to balance the continuation of education, while effectively running a hybrid environment within the education premises. Moreover, the social interactions in between students will support to enhance their mindsets to conduct their studies effectively and efficiently.

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